

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GIDEON****FIRST NAME: PETER NGADA****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing a good academic essay (EUCLID 2024, 1-4)
2. Researching the topic (EUCLID 2024, 8-9)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 27-35)
4. Latin abbreviation and expression (EUCLID 2024, 13)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 14)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

Period one of ACA-401D provides basic writing tips and has answered many questions every writer would ask; this course pack has streamlined a step-by-step approach to writing a good essay. It is important to note that writing a good essay requires basic steps and a well-structured format to present facts and arguments without any form of ambiguity. This course pack prepares students and professionals to learn about good academic essay writing, which involves clear and concise expression of ideas. ACA-401D pointed out the need for proper quotations, logical structure, and adherence to academic conventions in presenting a well-argued perspective supported by empirical evidence and critical analysis. Creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas (EUCLID 2024, 9).

2) TIPS FOR WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

It is also imperative to start up early, define the question and task at hand, and draft an initial plan to work with; good essay is subdivided into three parts: the introduction, the body, and the conclusion. This structure will help to communicate the ideas and make the

essay presentable and clear. Writing a good academic essay starts with identifying the purpose of the write-up; academic essays seek to provide an answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2024, 7).

Understanding the topic will guide one in researching the topic, and researching a topic allows facts and knowledge on the topic to be compiled. It is essential to make some notes while you read, as this will be the basis for your essay. However, in your initial reading photocopies, it is advised you underline or highlight relevant information, which you can return to when you re-read and take notes (EUCLID 2024, 8). Researching a topic gives you adequate knowledge to present your argument and facts about the topic; the result of your research will guide you in writing them down.

The course pack also pointed out the proper use of American and British, stating clearly the differences and similarities between the two; this will help students and writers make good use of the two. After reading through this subtopic, I saw clearly how British and American English varies in many aspects, from spelling to vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar. I understood that there are words in American and British English that are spelled differently yet with the same pronunciation and vice versa. Words with different pronunciations with the same spelling, same words but different or with additional meaning. American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English. Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural development (cf. *Are Americans Ruining English?* [PBS]) and the way in which the two national variants have changed correspondingly (EUCLID 2024, 25). Jargon also changes with cultural changes, which reflect changes in societal and popular cultural and technological preferences.

Latin abbreviations and expressions are largely used by technical communicators in academic writing and in many fields to transmit information and ideas in a clear manner. Examples of some Latin abbreviations are shown in the table below.

Table 1: Examples of Latin Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Latin	English
e.g	Exempli gratia	For example
i.e	id est	That is, in other words
Et al	Et alii/aliae	And other
cf	Confer	compare
e.t.c	Et cetera	And so forth

Examples of some commonly used Latin expressions are:

Ad hoc: meaning for this purpose

De facto: meaning in good faith.

In situ: meaning in its original place.

Per se: meaning by itself.

It is best to create content using "plain language" principles. Plain language (also called plain English) is a writing style that is simple and direct but not simplistic or patronizing. When writing in plain language, use short sentences with simple words. Avoid jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations. In the first reading, plain language should be visually inviting, logically organized, and understandable (EUCLID 2024, 59).

Plagiarism is a representation of someone else's work without acknowledging the author. EUCLID (2024, 34) simply put plagiarism as 'Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author'. Plagiarism is unprofessional and unethical; I also understand that plagiarism discourages hard work and undermines the authenticity of materials and facts. Plagiarism comes in two forms, both unacceptable. First, you plagiarize when you use the words of a source without quotation marks. If you take words from a source, you must use quotation marks, not just a footnote. Moreover, you should not present a close paraphrase from a source: either use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words (EUCLID 2024, 14).

3. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, good academic writing is a vital skill that facilitates effective communication, it requires paying attention to details and focusing on the structure of the essay, writing clearly, and drawing the reader's attention. With clear organization, evidence-based argumentation, and critical analysis, students and professionals can pen down compelling and credible academic work. This course pack provides students with all the tips for effective and well-structured writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.